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Socio-Economic Dynamics of Tribal Women Entrepreneurs in Jharkhand, India

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Abstract

Tribal women in India represent a unique socio-economic group marked by cultural richness, resilience, and strong community ties. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the role of tribal women entrepreneurs in rural and semi-urban economies, specially in agriculture, handicrafts, forest produce, and micro-enterprises. This research work critically examines the socio-economic conditions of 115 tribal women entrepreneurs in Ranchi Chhota-Nagpur region in Jharkhand state of India by analysing the key indicators such as income levels, education, access to credit and finance, ownership of assets, access to credits and digital media. Based on field studies and interviews of the respondents, government reports, and academic literature, the paper highlights the dynamics in socio-economic status due to their entrepreneurial setups and challenges these women face in navigating structural inequality, financial issues, and institutional gaps. It also concludes with inclusive growth, gender-sensitivity, and tribal-centric entrepreneurial ecosystems that uplift not only economic conditions but also social dignity and self-reliance.

Keywords: Tribal women, entrepreneurship, socio-economic status, entrepreneurial ecosystems, inclusive growth

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1. Introduction

Tribal communities have distinct social structures, customs, traditions, and ways of life that are deeply connected to their environment and natural resources. They often have a strong sense of identity and maintain a close relationship with their ancestral lands. Tribal communities are often culturally diverse, with unique languages, art forms, rituals, and belief systems (Singh et al., 2022). India, a nation of exceptional diversity, is characterised not only by its linguistic, religious, and cultural multiplicity but also by the intricate stratification of its populace along ethnic and social dimensions. The Scheduled Tribes (STs) constitute one of the most historically marginalised yet culturally affluent groups. According to the 2011 Census, the Scheduled Tribe population consists of approximately 104.5 million individuals, or about 8.6% of India's overall population. Their presence is particularly concentrated in the central tribal belt, which includes states such as Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, and Madhya Pradesh, as well as the North-Eastern region. These tribal groups, or *Adivasis*, make up a sizable community with a population of over 100 million India (Bhattacharya and Sachdev, 2021). However, the quality of life among tribal groups continues to be low due to a lack of accessibility, development, and long-term neglect. The tribal population of India is plagued by low literacy rates, high school dropout rates, malnutrition, and poverty (Islary, 2014; Brahmanandam and BosuBabu, 2016; Punnaiah, 2018). Tribal groups have always had a special bond with nature and use sustainable living methods. The tribal way of life is distinctive because it incorporates rituals for worshipping nature and land laws that grant communities collective rights (Gluckman, 2017; Kumar et al., 2020).

Jharkhand is the 28th state of India enriched with diverse flora-fauna and largest mineral-ore producing state of the country. The tribal population of Jharkhand, India, represents a crucial and defining element of the state's demographic and cultural identity. Jharkhand was established on November 15, 2000, as the 28th state of India. It is renowned for its natural riches, minerals, cultural uniqueness, and tribal variety. It is referred to as the "Ruhr of India" because to its substantial coal reserves (Chandra, 2013; Chandniha et al., 2017). The population is 32.99 million (2011), with 26.2% being tribal individuals. Jharkhand comprises 32 distinct tribal communities residing in 24 districts, 212 blocks, and 33,816 villages. The economic stability and livelihoods of tribal groups in Jharkhand are closely linked to their traditional ties to land, forests, and natural resources, yet they face mounting pressures from socio-political, economic, and environmental concerns. Over 60% of the tribal population in the state relies on agriculture as their principal means of income. The majority are marginal or

small-scale farmers with restricted access to irrigation, sophisticated agricultural methods, or institutional credit, leading to low production and seasonal employment. Data from many official and academic sources indicate that over 52.6% of Scheduled Tribe (ST) households in Jharkhand are involved in farming, while nearly 31% are employed as agricultural labourers, highlighting the increasing instability of land ownership and the transition towards daily-wage labour (Patel, 2014; Kandari, 2022). The condition of tribal women in Jharkhand is influenced by a distinctive combination of cultural resilience, economic involvement, and ongoing socio-economic difficulties. Tribal women in India, historically seen as guardians of culture, biodiversity, and indigenous knowledge, are progressively assuming entrepreneurial roles, signifying a notable transformation in the socio-economic structure of tribal communities. It is grounded in their indigenous knowledge systems that encompassing forest products, herbal medicine, bamboo crafts, weaving, and food processing tribal women are using these resources to establish sustainable, regionally anchored, and culturally resilient micro and small-scale enterprises. Tribal women entrepreneurs in Jharkhand face complex socio-economic and structural challenges that severely limit their engagement in entrepreneurial endeavours. A significant issue is their comparatively poor socio-economic status, marked by restricted access to productive assets, low literacy rates, limited mobility, and financial dependency, which collectively impede entrepreneurial risk-taking (Bhaumik & Coondoo, 2021). Nevertheless, tribal women entrepreneurs in Jharkhand persistently encounter systemic obstacles, including restricted access to formal education, financial resources, technology, transportation, and digital literacy. The entrenched patriarchal attitudes, insufficient legal understanding, and inadequate infrastructure amenities in rural and forested areas further impede their development (Nayak and Alam, 2022; Acherjee et al., 2023). The objective of this study is the assessment of the socio-economic study of specifically, the tribal women entrepreneur in Jharkhand state of India that provide insight in to income, education, occupation, housing, and asset ownership to understand the overall living status of tribal women. This is to examine the socio-economic dynamics among tribal women in Jharkhand, which is significant as it not only illustrates the economic behaviours and aspirations of an under-represented social group but also acts as a strategic avenue for equitable, sustainable, and culturally grounded development in India's tribal heartland.

2. Material and Methods

For the quantitative and qualitative study on tribal women entrepreneurs, data was collected from the Ranchi-South Chhotanagpur region using a structured schedule. Purposive sampling

and snowball sampling techniques were utilized to identify tribal women entrepreneurs. The data were gathered through the questionnaire cum interview schedule as primary data from 115 tribal women entrepreneurs from Ranchi-South Chhotanagpur region of Ranchi District in Jharkhand. The various factors and reasons including occupational, marital, economic, assets and social aspects related to tribal women entrepreneurship in this specific area were explored and studies. The gathered information was quantified and explained in terms of frequency (n) for number of respondent and percentage (%) using suitable statistical tools such as MS Excel (Microsoft, USA).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Socio-economic profile of the respondents

3.1.1. Locality

Locality plays an important role in survey research as it significantly influences the validity, relevance, and applicability of the obtained data. The distinct physical, cultural, and socio-economic backdrop of a region can offer distinctive elements that influence behaviours, needs, and perspectives (Zhang et al., 2024). The data in Table-1 indicated that most of the respondents (60 %) were from rural localities, whereas only 40 per cent represented the urban residents. This rural predominance underscores the significant presence and engagement of tribal women in entrepreneurial activities within non-urban environment. It also reflects the socio-geographic reality of the Ranchi-Chhotanagpur region, where a large proportion of the scheduled tribe population continues to inhabit rural landscapes.

3.1.2. Community profile

The data in Figure-1 indicated that most of the tribal women entrepreneur (57%) belonged to the Munda tribe followed by Santhal respondents who constituted 33 per cent of the sample. A smaller proportion, 10 per cent was from the Oraon tribe. Munda tribe was one of the predominant tribal communities as per the report from both the Chandramouli and General (2011) and the Ministry of Tribal Affairs (2025). These sources identify Munda, Santhal, and Oraon as the major scheduled tribe communities in Jharkhand, particularly in the Ranchi district, and highlight their socio-economic prominence. The predominance of Munda women in the sample reflects their demographic strength and comparatively higher participation in local entrepreneurial activities, supporting the representation pattern observed in this study.

3.1.3. Age of the respondents

Most of the respondents (51%) belonged to the 36-41 years age group, followed by 32 per cent in the 24-29 years category, and 17 per cent in the above 41 years group. This finding is supported by Lepcha (2021) and Naveen et al. (2023) who had reported that most of the respondents belong to the age group of 36-41 years engaged in entrepreneurial ventures.

3.1.4. Education

The analysis of respondent's education revealed that the most of the respondents (70 %) had received up to matric and intermediate level education. Whereas 20 % of the respondents had studied up to intermediate which was followed by the 2 % respondents who were illiterate as shown in the Table-1. The rise in higher education among women entrepreneurs in Jharkhand can be attributed to increasing social awareness, targeted educational interventions, and the longstanding influence of missionary-led educational institutions that historically prioritized literacy and empowerment among tribal populations. Previous research reports have indicated that missionary education has significantly expanded access to schooling for tribal girls, improving enrollment rates, retention, and overall educational attainment in states like Jharkhand (Kujur, 2019). Missionary schools in district like Ranchi have provided structured learning environments, vocational training, and value-based education, which collectively foster confidence, self-reliance, and leadership qualities critical traits for entrepreneurial development (Lakra & Tigga, 2020). Parallel to this, awareness campaigns launched by NGOs, state livelihood missions, and women-centered community organizations have increased understanding of the importance of higher education as a means for social mobility and economic independence (Tete, 2021).

3.1.5. Marital status

The marital status distribution of the respondents indicates a predominant representation of married women among the tribal women entrepreneurs surveyed. As illustrated in the chart, 70 per cent of the participants were married, highlighting the significant role of marital women in entrepreneurial engagement within the tribal communities. In contrast, 25 per cent of the respondents were unmarried, suggesting that a considerable proportion of younger or single women are also entering the domain of entrepreneurship. A small fraction, 5 per cent, comprised widowed women, reflecting their efforts toward economic self-reliance and resilience in the face of personal loss (Table-1). This data underscores the intersection of

marital status and entrepreneurial participation, which may have implications for support systems, decision-making autonomy, and access to resources among tribal women.

3.1.6. Types and Size of the family

The analysis of data revealed that a substantial majority nearly 70 per cent of the tribal women entrepreneurs belonged to joint families, indicating the continued prevalence of collective familial living arrangements in tribal society, 25 per cent of the respondents were from nuclear families, suggesting a moderate shift toward smaller, independent household structures. A minimal share, 5 per cent, reported living in extended family setups, which may include relatives beyond the immediate or joint family members (Table-1). Table indicates that 83 per cent of the respondents had small family size, while, 17 per cent were from medium-sized families of them had medium size of the family. The smaller family size may also be linked to greater manageability of household responsibilities, which can influence a woman's capacity to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Understanding family size is essential for assessing household labour dynamics, dependency ratios, and potential support or constraints in balancing domestic and economic roles. This finding is supported by Rafee (2024) who had reported that most of the respondents belong to the small size of the family.

3.1.7. Number of earning members

The analysis of the number of earning members within respondents' households reveals that most tribal women entrepreneurs operate in families with dual income sources. As represented in the chart, 79 per cent of the respondents reported having two earning members in their family, suggesting a shared economic responsibility between spouses or other family members. Moreover, 16 per cent of the respondents belonged to households with more than two earning members, reflecting a broader family-based economic engagement, possibly involving adult children or extended kin. A small proportion, 5 per cent, reported being the sole earner in their household, highlighting their economic vulnerability and sole responsibility for household income generation as given in Table-1. This data underlines the importance of family-level economic collaboration in tribal communities and may have implications for financial resilience, intra-household resource allocation, and the capacity to invest in micro-enterprise development.

Table-1: Social status of tribal women respondents

(n =115)

S. No	Particulars	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Locality	Urban	45	40
		Rural	70	60
2.	Community profile	Munda	66	57
		Santhal	38	33
		Oraon	11	10
3.	Age	18–23 years	-	-
		24–29 years	32	28
		30–35 years	10	09
		36–41 years	52	45
		Above 41 years	21	18
4.	Education	Illiterate	02	02
		Matric and Intermediate	81	70
		Graduate and above	32	28
5.	Marital Status	Unmarried	29	25
		Married	80	70
		Divorced	-	-
		Widow	06	05
6.	Type of Family	Nuclear	64	25
		Joint	40	70
		Extended	11	05
7.	Size of Family	Small (1–6)	95	83
		Medium (7–10)	20	17
		Large (11–15)	-	-
8.	Total Earning Members	One Member	06	05
		Two Member	91	79
		Three or more Member	18	16

3.1.8. Land Holdings

It is observed from Table-2 that among the respondents most of them (99 %) of the respondents possessed marginal landholdings, defined as up to 2.5 acres. Only 18 per cent of the respondents reported owning small landholdings, ranging from 2.5 to 5 acres. This finding is supported by Ashadagar (2021) who had reported that most of the respondents belong to the marginal land holdings in tribal areas.

3.1.9. Housing Types

Among the respondents, 82 per cent reside in pukka houses made of durable materials, 12 per cent live in kachha houses constructed with temporary materials, and 6 per cent occupy rented accommodations. This distribution reflects varying levels of housing security and access to infrastructure within the community. This finding is supported by Naveen, S. et al. (2023) and Arya (2018) who had reported that most of the respondents have pukka house followed by kaccha house constructed.

3.1.10. Availabilities of basic amenities

The survey shows that all respondents cent per cent (100%) have access to basic facilities such as electricity, drinking water, toilets, and internet. This indicates strong infrastructural development in tribal areas, especially Ranchi-Chhotanagpur, supporting better living conditions and enabling entrepreneurial activities through improved health, productivity, and digital connectivity. The universal access to basic facilities such as electricity, drinking water, toilets, and internet among the respondents aligns with the Ministry of Tribal Affairs (2020), which highlights significant infrastructural development in tribal regions as a driver of improved living standards and entrepreneurial growth. This is further reinforced by the Planning Commission of India (2011), which emphasized that access to such infrastructure is fundamental to the socio-economic empowerment of Scheduled Tribes and plays a vital role in fostering sustainable entrepreneurial opportunities in these areas.

3.1.11. Occupation of the respondents

The occupational profile of the respondents reveals a diverse engagement across various entrepreneurial sectors. A significant proportion of respondents 42 per cent were involved in food processing activities, making it the most prominent occupation among tribal women entrepreneurs in the study. This was followed by tailoring, which accounted for 17 per cent of the respondents. Service-based occupations, such as beauty parlours or similar personal

services, constituted 15 per cent of the sample. Handicraft-related and agriculture-related occupations were equally represented, with 13 per cent each. This distribution highlights the dominance of traditional and skill-based micro-enterprises, particularly food-related and tailoring ventures, among tribal women entrepreneurs in the Ranchi-Chhotanagpur region. These findings supported by several studies collectively highlight the growing role of entrepreneurship in transforming the socio-economic conditions of tribal women across India. Tribal women are actively engaged in a variety of occupations such as agriculture, food processing (e.g., pickle, papad, mahua laddoo), tailoring, bamboo, and handicrafts (like Dhokra-art, tribal jewellery making), herbal medicine and traditional healings, livestock rearing, and forest produce collection (e.g., mahua, lac, sal leaves, tendu). Many of these enterprises are home-based or supported by Self-Help Groups (SHGs), offering women an accessible pathway to economic independence (Seerangan & Ravi, 2024; Pandhare et al., 2024). Previous research works on the tribal regions like Jharkhand, Odisha, and Andhra Pradesh shows that these micro-enterprises enhance women's income, savings, decision-making power, and self-confidence (Rafee, 2024; Naveen et al., 2023).

The non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) and traditional crafts not only generate livelihood but also preserve indigenous knowledge and cultural identity (Singh & Das, 2023). Despite these positive outcomes, tribal women entrepreneurs face challenges such as limited market access, lack of technical training, weak infrastructure, and exploitation by middlemen (Bose and Sahu, 2022). The reviewed literature consistently emphasizes the need for supportive interventions including skill development, access to finance, infrastructure, and strong government-market linkages to ensure the sustainability and scalability of tribal women's entrepreneurial ventures (Sahoo and Patra, 2022; Kaur and Sharma, 2023). An overwhelming 93 per cent of the tribal women entrepreneurs surveyed identified marketing support as their most pressing need, while 7 per cent indicated a need for other types of support, and notably, none expressed a further need for training. This strong preference for marketing assistance suggests that while many tribal women have acquired foundational entrepreneurial skills, they now face challenges in accessing markets, promoting their products, and expanding their customer base. It highlights a critical gap in the value chain one that, if unaddressed, can limit the growth and sustainability of tribal enterprises. The absence of demand for additional training also implies a level of confidence and self-sufficiency developed through prior interventions. These insights underscore the need for targeted policies and initiatives focused on building market linkages, branding, and digital marketing platforms to strengthen the

entrepreneurial ecosystem for tribal women. Investments in rural infrastructure—road connectivity, storage facilities, energy, and digital networks are crucial for enhancing supply-chain efficiency and enterprise sustainability (Mehta & Sinha, 2021). Skill development programs could include lessons on branding, packaging, financial management, digital marketing, and value addition, presented in local tribal languages for enhanced understanding (Kerketta & Minz, 2021). Furthermore, promoting women's cooperatives, amalgamating indigenous knowledge systems with contemporary firms, and instituting childcare facilities to alleviate family responsibilities can enhance the entrepreneurial landscape (Lakra & Tigga, 2022). Consistent awareness programs must be executed to distribute information regarding government schemes, subsidies, and market prospects in tribal regions (Toppo & Lakra, 2023). These policy recommendations together seek to establish an inclusive and supportive environment attuned to the socio-cultural conditions of tribal women.

Figure-1: Respondents involved in various economic activities through their entrepreneurial ventures

3.1.12. Ownership of bank accounts and access to financial credit and loan utilization

The study found that all respondents (100 per cent) had functional bank accounts, reflecting full financial inclusion among tribal women entrepreneurs. This enables access to credit, savings, DBTs, and government schemes, marking a crucial step toward their economic empowerment and inclusion. The study also analyses credit access among tribal women entrepreneurs indicates a moderately high level of engagement with formal or informal lending sources. As shown in the chart, 55 per cent of the respondents reported having availed a loan, while the remaining 45 per cent had not accessed any form of credit. This suggests that more than half of the women have attempted to leverage financial instruments to support their entrepreneurial ventures. Many tribal women lack access to formal financial institutions, often due to the absence of collateral and discriminatory lending practices, resulting in dependence on informal credit sources that charge higher interest rates (Kumar & Mohanty, 2020).

3.1.13. Sources of Credit

Among the 115 tribal women entrepreneurs surveyed, 47 per cent (54 respondents) accessed credit through Self-Help Groups (SHGs), making it the most common source. While 19 per cent (22 respondents) relied on friends, family, or self-savings, while 5 per cent (6 respondents) took loans from private moneylenders. Only 3 per cent (3 respondents) availed credit from commercial banks, and 3 per cent (4 respondents) accessed government schemes such as MUDRA or PMEGP. Notably, no respondent reported receiving support from NGOs, and 23 per cent (26 respondents) had not availed any credit. These findings underscore the dominant role of SHGs and highlight gaps in formal and institutional credit access. These findings align with Singh and Jatav (2021), who emphasized the crucial role of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) in promoting financial inclusion and empowering tribal women by offering accessible, community-driven credit especially in rural and under banked regions. This is further reinforced by the Planning Commission of India (2014), which highlighted SHGs as key enablers of financial access, social cohesion, and economic participation among tribal communities in remote and underserved areas.

3.1.14. Access to media and digital platforms

The data shows that 67 per cent of tribal women entrepreneurs use mobile phones as their primary source of media, indicating strong digital penetration. About 28 per cent use both mobile phones and television, while only 5 per cent rely on newspapers. This trend reflects a shift toward digital platforms and highlights the need for targeted digital literacy and media

content suited to their socio-cultural context. The use of media platforms also facilitates participation in digital marketing, online learning, and entrepreneurial skill-building programs, which are crucial for marginalized groups with limited physical access to training centers (Pradhan & Das, 2022). In Jharkhand, tribal entrepreneurs specially women use social media not only for product promotion but also for storytelling and cultural branding that enhances the uniqueness of ethnic products and strengthens customer trust. Research shows that digital inclusion supports financial literacy and digital payments, enabling tribal entrepreneurs to integrate with formal financial systems through UPI, mobile banking, and micro-credit fintech tools (Kumar and Rout, 2020). Furthermore, digital visibility has allowed several tribal clusters to connect with NGOs, government livelihood missions such as JSLPS, and online marketplaces, facilitating improved supply chain linkages and entrepreneurial networking (Xaxa, 2021). Initially, the development of incubation centres and training hubs centred on tribal women, in collaboration with educational institutions, NGOs, and governmental bodies, can improve business acumen, foster creativity, and advance digital literacy (Sahu & Dwivedi, 2022).

Table-2: Assets, financial credits, and digital literacy of respondents

(n =115)

S. No	Particulars	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Total Land	Landless	-	-
		Marginal (Up to 2.5 acre)	89	78
		Small (2.5–5 acre)	21	18
		Medium (5–10 acre)	05	04
		Large (Above 10 acre)	-	-
2.	Housing Type	Kachha	14	12
		Pakka	94	82
		Rented	07	06
3.	Basic amenities	Yes	115	100
		No	-	-
4.	Ownership of Bank Accounts	Yes	115	100
		No	-	-
5.		Yes	63	55

	Access to Credit and Loan Utilization	No	52	45
6.	Sources of Credit	Commercial Bank	03	03
		Self-Help Group	54	47
		Government Scheme	04	03
		NGO or Development Organization	-	-
		Private Moneylender	06	05
		Friends or Family or self-saving	22	19
		Not availed any credit	26	23
7.	Access to media and digital platforms	Only Newspaper	06	05
		Only Television	-	-
		Only Radio	-	-
		Only Mobile	77	67
		Mobile and television both	32	28

4. Conclusion

The tribal women constitute an essential component of India's socioeconomic structure. This study extensively explores that many tribal women rely on agriculture, animal husbandry, retail, service, art and craft and forest-related activities, including the collection and processing of non-timber forest products such as lac, medicinal herbs, and fruits. The analysis reports that in tribal regions, where access to formal finance, markets, and higher education is often limited, SHGs act as a bridge that connects tribal women and households to economic opportunities, skill development, and institutional support. Their role extends beyond financial inclusion and contributes directly to social, economic, and psychological empowerment, making them a foundational pillar in tribal entrepreneurship. They are also strengthening entrepreneurship among tribal women requires not only skill development and financial access but also structural transformation through ecosystem-building, digital inclusion, infrastructural improvement, and culturally sensitive policy interventions. Therefore, empowering tribal women through entrepreneurship has the potential to uplift households, preserve traditional knowledge, create

sustainable livelihoods, and contribute to rural development in Jharkhand. Thus, promoting entrepreneurship among tribal women is both an economic imperative and a pathway toward social justice, cultural affirmation, and sustainable community transformation.

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6. Conflict of Research Interests

Authors declare no conflict of research interests.

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